

GEOZONE MARKETING AS AN ADVANTAGE IN THE DIGITAL PROMOTION STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT

Geozone marketing in the modern world is an extremely relevant and important tool for businesses from various industries. The purpose of the study is to determine the peculiarities of implementing geozone marketing based on the use of a strategic approach to promoting goods and services. The areas of application of geozone marketing in certain areas are proposed, taking into account global trends. The practical significance of the study lies in the possibility of applying such areas in the development of strategies for promoting goods and services by Ukrainian companies.

Keywords: marketing, geozone, strategy, marketing trends, tool, location.

Statement of the problem. Digital marketing is not just a tool, it is a new stage in the interaction between businesses and consumers, where digital technologies and electronic devices play a key role. We are moving from traditional methods to innovations, and a modern marketer must have a variety of tools, such as search engine optimization, content marketing, influencer marketing, and others. It is clear that today's consumer is not just an object of advertising, but an active participant who controls his or her interests and consumer aspirations.

In the context of globalization and constant changes in technology, it is important for marketers to be ready to adapt and use new strategies. It is digital marketing that allows marketers to move from standard approaches to individual communication with each client. The change in the consumer approach poses a challenge to marketing professionals, as it is important not only to offer goods and services, but also to build trust and create value for the consumer.

Literature review. The major trends in the development of marketing activities of business entities in the context of digital transformations and taking into account the conceptual foundations of strategic management are analyzed in the works of such researchers as Azhazha M. [1], Yevseitseva O. [2], Kapinus L. [3], Nemish Y. [4], Obikhod S. [5] and others. At the same time, the works of Gamova I. [6], Garmatyuk O. [7], Znachek R. [8], Ihnatenko R. [9] are devoted to topical

issues of practical use of digital marketing in the complex of promotion.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. Based on the analysis of the content of the theoretical and methodological studies of modern researchers in the field of digital marketing management, we note that to date, the issue of using some of its tools in the context of the geozone approach has not yet been resolved.

Purpose. The purpose of the study is to determine the peculiarities of implementing geozone marketing based on the use of a strategic approach to promoting goods and services.

Results. Current trends strongly suggest the dynamic development of the digital sphere in everyone's life. Nowadays, it is hard to imagine our daily existence without unlimited access to the Internet and related tools associated with this global network. Statistics at the beginning of 2022 show a significant increase – more than 62% of the world's population already has the ability to use the Internet [10]. The 3% increase compared to the previous year indicates an extremely dynamic development of the digital sphere (Tab. 1). The Internet continues to gain popularity and is becoming an essential part of modern life, providing many opportunities for communication, education, commerce, and entertainment. The analysis of Tab. 1 emphasizes the need to adapt and actively use Internet resources in the modern world.

Table 1

Total Internet users in Ukraine and the world in 2020-2022

Indicator	Year		
	2020	2021	2022
<i>the world index</i>			
Total population, mil. people	7750	7830	7910
Population aged 16 to 64 years, %	64,90	64,87	64,88
Number of Internet users, %	59,00	59,5	62,5
Absolute increase in the number of Internet users, %	-	+0,50	+3,00
<i>the Ukrainian index</i>			
Total population, mil. people	43,90	43,60	43,30
Population aged 16 to 64 years, %	66,00	65,90	64,50
Number of Internet users, %	63,00	67,60	71,80
Absolute increase in the number of Internet users, %	-	2,00	1,6

Source: [10]

There were 5.16 billion internet users in the world today according to the data of Digital 2023: Global Overview Report [11]. That meaning 64.4% of the world's total population was in early 2023. More than 66% of all the people on Earth at the beginning of 2024 use the Internet, with the latest data putting the global user total at 5.35 billion. Internet users have grown by 1.8% over the past 12 months, thanks to 97 million new users since the start of 2023 [12].

There were 28.57 million internet users in Ukraine at the start of 2023, when internet penetration stood at 79.2%. Ukraine was home to 26.70 million social media users in January 2023, equating to 74.0% of the total population [13].

So, today's marketing must be flexible, creative and result-oriented. Technological progress has become a challenge, but also an opportunity for those who are ready to learn new things and change approaches. Under these conditions, digital marketing is becoming not just a tool, but also the key to understanding and success in a world where communication and consumption are rapidly changing.

Based on the results of research conducted by Ukrainian and foreign scientists and marketers [4, 10, 14], it was identify the following trends in the development of digital marketing in 2023:

- expanded influence of the 5G network: thanks to the deployment of 5G technology, digital marketing will have new opportunities to use real-time information, streaming high-quality video and interactive applications;
- development of virtual and augmented reality (VR and AR): the use of VR and AR in marketing campaigns will become more widespread, providing users with an immersive and immersive experience;
- interactive content: the growing popularity of interactive content, such as voice searches, real-time polls, and other forms of audience interaction;
- increasing role of video marketing: video remains a key element of marketing strategies, and its role will be further enhanced by the popularity of short videos and streaming platforms;
- artificial intelligence in marketing: the use of AI to personalize content, analyze data, predict trends and automate marketing tasks;

- content in the format of event feeds or "Stories" on social media platforms will continue to gain popularity, providing companies with the opportunity to tell stories more effectively;

- the effective use of chatbots: the increased use of chatbots to interact with customers, resolve their issues and even make purchases directly through chat;

- expanding the use of blockchain technology to increase security and transparency in advertising campaigns and financial transactions;

- environmental responsibility in marketing and growing support for sustainable development ideas;

- increasing the influence of social media, expanding social media marketing strategies using new features and advertising opportunities.

The identified trends are also accompanied by the development and evolution of digital marketing tools and methods: the use of the Internet of Things (IoT) is expanding; the use of analytics and BigData is growing; personalized advertising strategies based on consumer data are developing; location-based marketing technologies are being applied, etc.

In particular, as digitalization deepens and location-based technologies develop, geozone marketing is emerging as a new stage in the evolution of consumer marketing, providing companies with extraordinary opportunities to attract and retain customers. Geozone marketing is a strategy for using location data to personalize marketing efforts. The lack of location ties is limited by the use of geozone, which allow you to define specific areas to intensify marketing campaigns [15]. Using GPS, Bluetooth, NFC, and other technologies, geozone can pinpoint the exact location of users, creating unique opportunities for personalized offers and interactive events. It allows creating accurate and personalized campaigns.

With accurate location data, offers and advertisements can be customized to the specific context and interests of consumers. With special offers and discounts for users in specific geographies, businesses can significantly increase conversion and drive purchases. Creating unique content for users in specific geographies helps to attract attention and improve brand perception. For retailers, geozone is an ideal tool for attracting customers, driving sales, and increasing brand awareness.

By providing consumers with personalized offers, geozone marketing promotes convenience and comfort in the process of interacting with products and services. In addition, geozone allows collecting detailed analytics on customer behavior in specific geographic areas, which enables to continuously improve strategies and increase the effectiveness of marketing campaigns.

Geozone marketing uses a customer account to interact with users in certain areas of activity (Tab. 2). Overall, geozone marketing offers businesses a powerful tool to deliver relevant and timely messages to their target audience based on their location, helping to increase engagement, drive traffic, and boost sales.

Table 2

Areas of application of geozone marketing

Field of application	Meaning and direction of use
Retail	Send special offers and discounts to stores when a potential customer is nearby
Restaurants and cafes	Geozone allows restaurants and cafes to send special offers or discount coupons to attract customers when they are near the location
Mobile applications	Applications that are downloaded to the site may send users personalized information, advertisements, or offers based on their geographic location
Transport	Transport companies can use geozone to send information about schedules, fare discounts, or special offers to users in a particular region
Events and activities	Event promoters can use geozone to send messages about events, schedules, and special activities to attendees who are at the location
Banking and financial services	Banks and financial institutions can use geo-fencing to send offers of favorable service conditions or other financial offers to customers who are close to their branches
Museums and landmarks	Geozone can be used to boost exclusive offers and information about exhibitions when visitors are in museums, exhibition centers, or other places of cultural and historical value
Tourism and hospitality	Hotels and travel companies can use geozone to increase information about special offers, excursions or restaurants, and other related services when a tourist is in a certain location

Source: developed by the authors

As for the global experience of using geofencing in the strategy of promoting products and services, an example can be given for Uber, which implements zoning to provide services where there are organizational restrictions. For example, geofences help Uber to send notifications to app users about available taxis in the area of their trip, even if the administration of an airport or other facility has banned the use of such cars on its territory. All the customer needs to do is look at their smartphone and get into a car near the geozone.

Another example is the marketing strategies of Starbucks, which is not just a leader in the service industry and a world-famous brand, but also a well-known pioneer in geozone marketing. Push notifications from Starbucks about happy hours not only help to attract the attention of a person who is in the coffee shop area, make a bargain and buy a favorite drink for half the price, but also allow you to segment the target audience, study their preferences in relation to real time and location.

Overall, these examples show how geozone can be successfully used in various industries to attract attention and engage customers in specific places and moments.

Conclusions. Thus, the development of geozone marketing opens up many opportunities for effective and accurate interaction with the audience, which makes it an important step in the continuous development of consumer marketing. In particular, the use of geozone marketing is relevant in the modern world due to several important factors: personalization of offers, increased conversion, optimization of advertising budgets, improved customer interaction, increased competitiveness, etc. Geozone marketing is not just a

new tool. It is a transition to individualized and extremely effective consumer interaction. The use of geozone marketing is becoming a strategic element for businesses seeking to optimize their marketing strategies and maximize their impact on the target audience.

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